

Polar Nature of Isobutyryl Chloride

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From conductance, cryoscopic and spectral studies of the solution of isobutyryl chloride in disulphuric acid, its chloride ion donor character is established; isobutyryl chloride forms stable complexes with Lewis acids and bases. From infra-red spectra and molar conductance values, these compounds have been found to be ionic in nature. Conductometric and visual titrations between Lewis acid and base have been carried out in isobutyryl chloride. Solvolytic reactions have also been carried out to support its mode of self ionisation.

Extensive investigations have been carried out, using acid halide as solvents¹⁻³ and acid-base reactions based upon their self ionisations have been reported in them. Drago and co-workers⁴, however, have postulated that there is no need for the self ionisation of

FIG 1 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS BETWEEN LEWIS ACIDS AND BASES IN ISOBUTYRYL CHLORIDE AT 25°C

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the solvent because conductometric titrations between solvoacids and bases can be explained through the co-ordination model. Paul and co-workers⁵⁻⁷ from conductance and infra-red spectral studies of the solid complexes of acetyl chloride and bromide with Lewis acids and bases have postulated their mode of self ionisation as $\text{CH}_3\text{COX} \rightleftharpoons \text{CH}_3\text{CO}^+ + \text{X}^-$. But in case of phosphoryl chloride⁸ and bromide and selenyl chloride⁹, the solid complexes with Lewis acids have been shown to co-ordinate through oxygen atom and they do not appear to be chloride ion donor solvents. It has, therefore, been of interest to investigate the solvent potentialities of isobutyryl chloride and establish its mode of self ionisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isobutyryl chloride was prepared by refluxing thionyl chloride and isobutyric acid¹⁰. Lewis acids and bases were purified by the usual methods. Aprotic solvents for molar conductance were dried by keeping them over molecular sieves for 48 hrs and were distilled before use. Disulphuric acid of exact composition was prepared from its conductance and freezing point measurements. Cryoscopic set up and method of determining freezing point was exactly the same as used by Gillespie and Malhotra¹¹. Conductometric titrations were carried out in a conductivity cell having a cell constant 0.32 cm^{-1} and the conductance of the solution was measured at $25.0^\circ \pm 0.02^\circ$, using a precision measuring bridge type WBR No. 108 with logarithmic indicator amplifier type TAV. IKC No. 034 (Wissenschaftliche Technische Werkstätten, Weilheim/oby, Germany).

The method of the preparation of the adduct of Lewis acids and bases with isobutyryl chloride is exactly the same as used by Paul and co-workers¹².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Disulphuric acid is a molecularly dissociated and slightly self ionised solvent¹³. Bases are protonated in it as :

and ionisable chlorides are changed to chlorosulphuric acid as :

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By studying the behaviour of acid halides in disulphuric acid, it has been possible to differentiate whether they have ionisable halide ions or more basic oxygen atom¹⁴. Isobutyryl chloride is exothermally soluble in disulphuric acid. It may behave in either way depending on whether it has more basic oxygen (i) atom or has ionisable halide ions (ii).

Conductometric and cryoscopic factors γ and ν suggest that isobutyryl chloride behaves according to equation (ii). Cryoscopic titrations of these solutions against sulphur trioxide show that two moles of sulphuric acid are produced per mole of isobutyryl chloride. Infra-red spectrum of concentrated solutions shows a sharp absorption band at 2300 cm^{-1} which is due to $\text{R}-\text{C} \equiv \text{O}^+$ absorption frequency and supports the mode as represented by equation (ii) and consequently the chloride ion character of isobutyryl chloride. Absorption bands corresponding to the anions could not be observed due to the complicated spectrum of the solvent itself.

Further information on the nature of isobutyryl chloride is obtained from a study of the complexes of isobutyryl chloride with Lewis acids and bases. Lewis acids such as antimony pentachloride, tin-tetrachloride, boron-trichloride and titanium tetrachloride form solid complexes with isobutyryl chloride in liquid sulphur dioxide at -40° .

TABLE 1

Acid	Stoichiometric composition	Physical State Colour and m.p.	Conductance at 25° ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Analysis			
				Metal % found	Metal % reqd.	Chlorine % found	Chlorine % reqd.
Boron trichloride	BCl ₃ .A	White solid 118°D	16.46	5.04	4.86	42.84	43.40
Antimony pentachloride	SbCl ₅ .A	White solid 142°D	18.34	29.86	30.00	51.80	52.48
Tin tetrachloride	SnCl ₄ .2A	White solid 138°D	32.68	22.04	22.96	44.04	44.92
Titanium tetrachloride	TiCl ₄ .2A	Yellow solid 124°D	36.16	17.38	18.80	52.16	52.82

A stands for (CH₃)₂CHCOCl.

These compounds are moisture sensitive but quite stable at room temperature in the dry atmosphere. From molar conductance values in aprotic solvents (Table I) they have been found to be ionic compounds. Infra-red spectra of these compounds also support the ionic nature of these compounds. The band at 1730 cm⁻¹ which is due to the C = O frequency in isobutyryl chloride has completely disappeared whereas a new band corresponding to -C ≡ O⁺ stretching vibration has appeared around 2270 cm⁻¹ depending upon the acceptor strength of the Lewis acid. From Table 2 it is found that isobutyryl chloride forms acyl

TABLE 2

Principal bands (cm⁻¹) of the complexes of Lewis acids with Isobutyryl chloride

(CH ₃) ₂ CHCOCl.BCl ₃	(CH ₃) ₂ CHCOCl.SbCl ₅	[(CH ₃) ₂ CHCOCl] ₂ SnCl ₄
2270	2290	2282
1450	650	510
1380	334	312
1275	280	
690		
660		

ion upon combination with strong chloride ion acceptors. The other bands present in the spectra are due to the anions. The broad and strong bands at 280, 334 and 650 cm⁻¹ may be due to the hexachloro antimonate ion [SbCl₆]⁻, the bands at 1455, 1380, 1275 and 690 cm⁻¹ are due to the tetrachloroborate ion [BCl₄]⁻ and the bands at 510 and 312 cm⁻¹ are due to the hexachloro stannate ion [SnCl₆]²⁻. It therefore, may be concluded that boron-trichloride, antimony pentachloride and stannic chloride form ionic complexes by accepting chloride ion from isobutyryl chloride, *i.e.*,

Ionic nature of these adducts finds further support from the X-ray studies of the adduct¹⁵ $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOCl}\cdot\text{SbCl}_5$ and supports the chloride ion donor character of isobutyryl chloride.

Acid-halides are known to form addition complexes with organic tertiary bases but literature lacks information on such complexes of isobutyryl chloride. Paul and co-workers⁶, from the infra-red studies of the complexes of acetyl chloride and organic tertiary bases have shown the chloride ion donor character of acetyl chloride. A large number of the complexes of isobutyryl chloride and organic tertiary bases have been prepared. Their stoichiometric composition has been confirmed by elemental analysis (Table 3). It was observed that one mole of the base reacts with one mole of isobutyryl chloride. Molar conductance values of these complexes in various solvents (where solubility permitted) suggest their ionic character. These complexes are hygroscopic and fume in moisture.

TABLE 3

Base	Stoichiometric composition	Physical state colour and m.p. ($^{\circ}\text{D}$)	Molar conductance at 25° ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$	Analysis			
				Chlorine % found	Chlorine % reqd.	Base % found	Base % reqd.
Pyridine	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}\cdot\text{A}$	White solid 134°	18.64*	19.49	19.13	42.14	42.58
Quinoline	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}\cdot\text{A}$	Pale solid 124°	15.08*	15.36	15.07	55.37	54.78
α -picoline	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}\cdot\text{A}$	Pale solid 132°	48.69**	17.44	17.85	47.12	46.65
Dimethylaniline	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{N}\cdot\text{A}$	Pale solid 106°	17.40*	16.92	16.78	52.16	51.53
Morpholine	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{NO}\cdot\text{A}$	White solid 96°	52.36**	17.90	18.36	44.08	44.96
Triethyl amine	$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{N}\cdot\text{A}$	White solid 88°	64.92**	17.46	17.11	47.59	48.68
Ethylene diamine	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\cdot\text{A}$	White solid 102°	50.52**	21.08	21.61	36.20	35.26

A = $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\cdot\text{COCl}$.

* = Nitrobenzene.

** = Nitromethane.

Further support to the ionic nature of isobutyryl chloride is provided by the infra-red studies of the complexes. Though we have examined the spectra of all the complexes, yet for brevity, only the spectra of three complexes is being reported. It is observed in these complexes that the spectral bands of the pure components change on complex formation. On complex formation, the spectral bands of the pure components undergo the same changes as occur in the formation of pyridinium chloride¹⁶ $[\text{PyH}^+\text{Cl}^-]$ and also in case of the compound of selenium tetrachloride and pyridine¹⁷. The band at 3005 cm^{-1} in pyridine assigned to C-H (of the ring) stretch shifts to lower spectral region. The strong bands of pyridine at 1583 , 1572 , 1483 and 1439 cm^{-1} assigned to C=C and C=N vibrations are replaced by the bands at 1630 , 1605 , 1525 and 1480 cm^{-1} in case of the spectrum of the pyridine complex. The shifts in all these cases is in the same direction and is nearly of the

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same magnitude as have been reported for pyridine chloride. Similar behaviour is observed for the absorption bands at 785 and 705 cm^{-1} assigned for the ring deformation in pyridine which shifts to 760 and 680 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the complex which shows the pyridine is present as pyridinium ion. A similar trend of perturbations in the vibrational frequencies of different groups present in other tertiary bases occur on complex formation with isobutyryl chloride. In the case of pyridine and other bases with isobutyryl chloride a new band at 2150–2200 cm^{-1} due to acyl ion $\text{R}-\text{C} \equiv \text{O}^+$ has also been assigned. The structure of these bases may be assigned as :

TABLE 4

Infra-red Spectral frequencies (cm^{-1}) of complexes of Isobutyryl chloride with organic bases

A	B	C	D
2840 S	2980 S	2900 m	2860 m
2140 m	2520 S	2600 S	2620 S
1631 S	2200 m	2130 m	2150 m
1602 S	1650 S	1648 S	1650 S
1530 S	1605 S	1620 m	1606 S
1480 S	1560 m	1600 S	1535 m
1370 m	1510 W	1540 m	1470 S
1250 S	1470 S	1480 S	1370 m
1198 S			
1160 S	1380	1380 S	1306 m
1058 S	1270 S	1305 m	1250 S
1000 S	1265 S	1260 S	1140 S
760 VS	1200 S	1210 S	1050 S
680 VS	1160 S	1120 S	1008 S
A $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOCl} \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	1040 S	1045 S	940 m
	970 m	1010 S	720 S
B $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOCl} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$	950 S	960 m	680 S
C $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOCl} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$	930 S	720 S	
D $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCOCl} \cdot \text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$	880 S	700 S	
	840 S		
	760 S		

As these complexes are ionic in nature and have ionisable chloride ions, therefore it has been of some interest to investigate their behaviour in disulphuric acid, where they would behave like other chloride ion donors as :

However, from cryoscopic and conductance studies they have been found to behave as :

It may be because in disulphuric acid the proton (H^+) is a far stronger acid than RCO^+ and hence RCO^+ is replaced by the proton in these complexes. From all these observations it may be concluded that isobutyryl chloride is a chloride ion donor and its mode of ionisation may be represented as :

Further light on the nature of isobutyryl chloride has been thrown by carrying out acid-base titrations conductometrically in the solvo system isobutyryl chloride. In figure 1 are given the conductometric titration curves for antimony pentachloride and tetrabutyl ammonium chloride along with those of borontrichloride and various organic tertiary base. Acid-base neutralisation reaction may be represented as :

where B^* stands for tertiary base. When the compound $\text{RCOB}^*.\text{BCl}_4$ is heated under reduced pressure, it loses a solvent molecule as

In case of stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride there are two breaks in the conductance-composition curves corresponding to the molar ratio base/acid of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1, confirming to the dibasic character of these Lewis acids. The solid complexes have already been shown to be ionic in nature and as these titrations can be followed conductometrically, therefore the presence of ions in solutions is also confirmed and the acid-base reaction can, therefore, may be postulated as :

When the neutral salt is heated under reduced pressure, it loses solvent molecule as :

Similarly, in case of titanium tetrachloride, acid-base titrations can be explained through ion formation.

Visual titrations between Lewis acids and bases in isobutyryl chloride have been carried out to further support the ionic nature of isobutyryl chloride. Crystal violet, malachite green and methylene blue have been used as the internal indicators. It is observed that the changes in the colour of these indicators at the end point is exactly the same as in case of water and the end points are quite sharp. The reversible character of these indicators has also been confirmed. These visual titrations also support the ionic character of isobutyryl chloride. This technique has already been used in acetyl chloride¹⁸, benzoyl chloride¹⁹ and other acid halides.

Further support is lent to the ionic character and the mode of ionisation of the solvent by carrying out solvolytic reactions in it. These are important set of reactions which a solute may undergo when dissolved in a polar solvent and may be regarded as occurring between the ionic species of the solute and those of the solvent and have been carried out in most of the solvents for preparative work and to support their modes of ionisation. Solvolytic reactions in selenyl chloride²⁰, acetyl chloride²¹, benzoyl chloride²², ethyl acetate²³ have been carried out to support their modes of ionisation. It is observed that some oxides, formates, oxalates, carbonates, acetates, sulphates, nitrites and nitrates of metals undergo solvolytic reactions when dissolved in isobutyryl chloride and are converted to the corresponding chlorides. In some cases the solvolytic reaction proceeds at room temperature where as in other cases the mixture has to be refluxed for 10–48 hrs. for the complete solvolysis. The mode of solvolysis for most of the solutes has been found out by characterising the end products.

In case of selenium dioxide, isobutyryl chloride forms selenium tetrachloride and isobutyric anhydride (b.p 185°). The solvolytic reaction is instantaneous even at room temperature and the mode of solvolysis may be presented as :

The formation of isobutyric anhydride supports the mode of its ionisation as postulated above. Silver nitrate when solvolysed forms silver chloride which is insoluble in isobutyryl chloride. The other products which have been characterised are nitrosyl chloride and isobutyric anhydride. Solvolytic reaction may be postulated through the formation of ions as :

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Isobutyric nitrate so formed during the reaction decomposes on heating to form isobutyric anhydride and oxides of nitrogen as :

However, in the presence of excess of isobutyryl chloride, isobutyryl nitrate forms nitrosyl chloride as :

From all these observations, it may be concluded that isobutyryl chloride ionises to form acyl ion and chloride ion and the mode of its ionisation may be postulated as :

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